

Antisemitism after 7 October 2023 from the Perspective of Sartre

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Introduction

Since the Hamas attacks of 7 October 2023, antisemitic incidents increased significantly across Europe and the United States, with hostile rhetoric and harassment emerging from far-right, radical-left, and Islamist milieus alike (ADL 2024; CST 2024a; Marone 2025:1). This unusual convergence, marked by mass demonstrations, shared slogans, and the rapid spread of anti-Jewish tropes, indicates that the post-7-October environment is not merely a reaction to political events, but the activation of deeper cognitive and ideological patterns (Stögner 2025:18; Enstad 2023:25-26). Understanding why these responses emerged so quickly, and why they display such emotional rigidity, requires philosophical analysis in addition to sociological data. The current moment therefore, offers a pressing case for revisiting classical theories of antisemitism. The essay argues that Sartre provides a compelling but incomplete explanation of post-7-October antisemitism. His concept of antisemitism as a self-chosen passion illuminates its emotional rigidity and resistance to facts, but Arendt's philosophical analysis better explains its structural, historical, and political dimensions that Sartre's existential psychology cannot supply. To defend this thesis, the paper proceeds as follows. First, it clarifies essential conceptual distinctions relevant to contemporary antisemitism, including the difference between legitimate political criticism and ideological hostility. Second, the essay presents Sartre's existential account of antisemitism as a chosen passion grounded in bad faith, showing how it illuminates recent empirical developments. Third, it exposes the limitations of Sartre's framework, especially its tendency to psychologize what is also a political and ideological phenomenon. Fourth, the essay turns to Arendt's critique, which reconceives antisemitism not as a psychological need but as a modern political ideology embedded in institutional

structures. The paper then argues that Arendt's view completes what Sartre left unexplained. It concludes by showing why both existential and structural accounts are necessary for understanding and responding to contemporary antisemitism.

Concepts

There is an important distinction between hostility against Jews as Jews and legitimate political criticism of Israel. The International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance (IHRA) working definition frames antisemitism as a particular perception of Jews that can manifest as hatred. This hatred may include rhetorical or physical acts against Jewish individuals, communities, or institutions. Philosophically, the most paramount part of this definition is that it treats antisemitism as a form of identity-based projection, meaning that blame is attributed to Jews as such, not as a result of their actions. This provides a conceptual baseline to distinguish ideological hostility from non-antisemitic political disagreement (IHRA 2016; European Commission and IHRA 2021:9–10).

The Jerusalem Declaration on Antisemitism (JDA) refines this distinction. It explicitly separates political critique from collective attribution. The JDA defines antisemitism as discrimination, prejudice, or hostility toward Jews, but stresses that criticism of Israeli policy is legitimate unless it relies on essentializing claims about Jews as a group (Jerusalem Declaration Group 2021). The JDA therefore emphasizes intention, context, and identity, offering a conceptual tool for identifying when discourse shifts from political criticism to ideological hostility. It also aims to prevent the conceptual overreach sometimes associated with IHRA and explicitly seeks to safeguard space for critical political dialogue by encouraging contextual analysis of contested speech (Deckers and Coulter 2022:734).

Both frameworks agree that political criticism becomes antisemitic when it draws on essentialist assumptions about Jews as a group. While the IHRA working definition helps identify forms of antisemitism, the JDA definition helps determine whether particular criticisms rely on ideological generalizations. Both also acknowledge that antisemitism can surface through anti-Israel sentiments, though not all such criticism crosses that line (Stögner 2025:2). This complementary structure allows IHRA to function as an identification tool and JDA as an interpretive guide. These definitional debates matter for philosophical reasons as they determine how we distinguish between reason-guided political critique and identity-based hostility, a distinction central to Sartre's and Arendt's

analyses. They also matter for safeguarding minority rights, freedom of expression, and the quality of public political discourse.

From a liberal-egalitarian perspective, impartiality requires that similar cases be treated alike unless a relevant difference justifies unequal treatment. Antisemitism, understood conceptually, violates this norm by introducing double standards: applying the same rule more harshly to Jewish or Jewish institutions without relevant justification (Greene, Cheng, and Kingsbury 2021:3-5; Cecchinato 2024:68-79). Formally, a double standard is the differential application of the same norm to like cases without a relevant difference, and, diagnostically, it becomes visible when a principle is applied more harshly to a Jewish case than to a comparable non-Jewish one. This mechanism is ethically significant because it turns universal principles into tools of selective moral judgment (Stögner 2025:14), a dynamic that will later align with Sartre's account of bad faith and Arendt's account of ideological scapegoating.

Moreover, these patterns challenge the view that prejudice comes from ignorance and that education always leads to tolerance (Greene, Cheng, and Kingsbury 2021:2–4). In fact, empirical evidence rather suggests that individuals with higher education levels can be more prone to applying double standards toward Jewish cases. This is especially troubling because these individuals are precisely the actors for whom the application of imperial rule matters most in institutions, and it shows that the common view is insufficient, as knowledge and degrees do not guarantee impartiality. Philosophically, this reinforces Sartre's claim that antisemitism is not corrected by additional information because it expresses a pre-rational commitment rather than a factual misunderstanding (Greene, Cheng, and Kingsbury 2021:6–7, 10–12).

The asymmetrical application of universal norms is not only philosophically incoherent (Stögner 2025:18) but also has concrete implications for political freedom. The protection of minority rights concerns the conditions under which individuals can live openly without fear or self-censorship. Empirical evidence that about one-third of Jews refrain from displaying visible markers of identity in public indicates not just a discomfort but also a significant restriction of this freedom (Enstad 2023:1, 21–22). This provides contemporary support for Sartre's insight that antisemitism constrains existential agency and forces individuals into forms of bad faith.

Sartre's perspective

The conceptual framework established above, identity-based projection, unequal rule-application, and pre-rational commitments, mirrors several mechanisms that the French philosopher Jean-Paul Sartre (1905 – 1980) identifies in *Anti-Semite and Jew*. Sartre argues that antisemitism functions not merely as an attitude but as a project aimed at excluding Jews from the social and political community, extending to the erosion of their rights and civic belonging. For Sartre, this project precedes empirical observation: the anti-Semite begins with a pre-fabricated image of “the Jew” and subsequently interprets all facts through this lens. The essay now turns to Sartre’s perspective to examine how he understands antisemitism as a chosen passion grounded in bad faith. Bad faith, as Sartre defines it, is a mode of self-deception in which consciousness attempts to flee the burden of freedom by treating itself as fixed and determined (Sartre [1943] 1956:47-70).

Sartre claims that antisemitism is not just a personal opinion or social attitude but a passion actively chosen. Opinions can be debated or changed, but a passion is not guided by reason. It expresses a person’s overall stance toward the world, what he calls a “free and total choice of oneself” (Sartre [1948] 1976:11). For this reason, Sartre insists that antisemitism is not a judgment formed from evidence but a prior existential commitment that shapes how evidence is perceived. Further, for Sartre, the anti-Semite does not hold a belief about Jews; he rather adopts a stance that precedes facts and remains immune to them. This is why any contradiction feels similar on a personal attack to the anti-Semite: it threatens the worldview they have already chosen. As a result, discussion no longer aims at finding the truth. Further, Sartre controversially asserts, “if the Jew did not exist, the anti-Semite would invent him”, capturing that the figure of “the Jew” is a psychological construction that fulfills the anti-Semite’s need for simplicity, certainty, and blame. In this frame, antisemitism originates not in Jewish actions but in an existential desire to reject ambiguity and responsibility (Sartre [1948] 1976:4-8).

For Sartre, antisemitism is above all a choice about how to relate to the world, not an outcome of misinformation or misinterpretation. He argues that the anti-Semite chooses a worldview that protects him from the demands of freedom, responsibility, and ambiguity (Sartre [1948] 1976:6–9). This stance provides emotional security by offering simple, unambiguous explanations for complex social problems. It thereby furnishes the anti-Semite with feelings of certainty, superiority, and security, satisfying emotional needs rather than responding to reality. In embracing antisemitism, the anti-Semite adopts a

position that precedes any encounter with facts, and it is a way of being in the world rather than an empirical judgment. Sartre thus presents antisemitism as a mode of emotionally organizing the world: a framework that channels blame outward and stabilizes the anti-Semite's sense of identity. This is why evidence does not challenge antisemitism but instead is reinterpreted within a self-sealing framework. Sartre writes that the anti-Semite seeks the illusion of a world closed, solidified, and beyond ambiguity (Sartre [1948] 1976:9), which explains why contradictory information feels threatening.

Sartre interprets antisemitism as a particular form of bad faith, the kind of self-deception he develops in *Being and Nothingness* (Sartre [1943] 1956:47-70). In bad faith, a person refuses to acknowledge their own freedom and responsibility, instead adhering to a fixed role or attitude because it feels safer than facing uncertainty. For Sartre, the anti-Semite accepts evidence that would unsettle the worldview they have chosen, so they avoid genuine reasoning and turn discussion into a "game" designed to silence or intimidate rather than to persuade (Sartre [1948] 1976:7–10). Antisemitism thus functions as a deliberate strategy of bad faith: a way of constructing a closed world in which one's prejudices cannot be challenged, and the burden of freedom is denied.

Sartre argues that everyone lives in a particular "situation," encompassing a blend of social, historical, economic, and political contexts. Even though the situation is shaped by the aforementioned facticities, individuals shape their reality through free choices, where freedom is not just an abstract idea but is rooted in how we define existence. Sartre further describes the "paradox of freedom," which means that freedom entails taking responsibility for the meaning one creates. For instance, the waiter or prisoner must confront their situation, make choices, and give their life and its circumstances meaning. Sartre emphasizes that this comes with torment, as we confront our freedom. However, the paradox is that freedom needs constraints to be meaningful, as circumstances do not dictate but condition, forming a reciprocal relationship (Sartre [1943] 1956:433 – 556). Sartre distinguishes between authentic and inauthentic Jews. Inauthenticity is similar to bad faith, while authenticity means facing up to one's freedom and the challenges it entails, and consciously accepting and supporting projects that give meaning to one's life. Sartre argues that antisemitic stereotypes capture various aspects of the behavior of inauthentic Jews, who try to hide or flee their Jewishness. This suggestion is flawed from the outset, though, as it de facto perpetuates those stereotypes. By implying that inauthentic Jews resemble the images projected by anti-Semites, Sartre risks reinforcing the very caricatures he seeks to

criticize. Even if unintentional, this framing implies that some Jews “live up to” antisemitic myths by not confronting their identity in the right way. (Sartre [1948] 1976:65–102).

A central component of Sartre’s analysis is that the figure of “the Jew” is not derived from Jewish people themselves but is invented by the anti-Semite. Sartre describes that the anti-Semite begins not with observation but with a preconceived notion of “the Jew” and then selects or distorts facts to fit this pre-established image (Sartre [1948] 1976:10–12). In this process, language itself becomes rigid as terms such as “the Jew” function not as descriptors but as fixed labels through which myths, insinuations, and slogans replace rational argument. The purpose of this image is not understanding but confirmation: antisemitism is a closed system in which every piece of evidence is reinterpreted to reinforce the myth. For this reason, Sartre rejects any notion that Jewishness could be anchored in biological or racial categories, as the identity the anti-Semite invokes is not empirical but a product of prejudice. In his view, the supposed “essence” of the Jew is constructed by antisemitism itself, not derived from Jewish people’s lived reality.

Information that contradicts the stereotype is dismissed or transformed into further proof of Jewish duplicity, whereas information that supports the myth is amplified. Sartre describes this as a process of projection in which the anti-Semite externalizes his own fears and contradictions, attributing them to an imagined Other. This mechanism aligns with the structure of bad faith because consciousness flees its own ambiguity by identifying wholly with a fixed role and by fabricating fixed identities for others (Sartre [1943] 1956:57–65). The “Jew” is thus not an empirical category but a mythical construction that stabilizes the anti-Semite’s self-deception.

Sartre emphasizes that antisemitism serves as an emotional function for the anti-Semite. It provides a simplified interpretation of the world. Rather than facing uncertainty or acknowledging responsibility, the anti-Semite turns toward a passion that transforms complexity into a single, fixed explanation. Antisemitism, further, gives its adherents a kind of emotional clarity, as all problems appear to have one cause, and all anxieties can be projected outward. Because of that, the anti-Semite is someone who wants to feel persecuted because persecution confirms the worldview he has already chosen.

Antisemitism thus becomes a psychological refuge, an attitude that converts personal insecurity into hate and turns failures or frustrations into evidence of Jewish wrongdoing. It provides the anti-Semite with unity, certainty, and a sense of belonging, precisely because it eliminates the restrictions of thinking and shields him from ambiguity. Sartre sees this as a refusal of existential freedom itself, an attempt to escape the ambiguity and responsibility

that accompany authentic human existence. For Sartre, this emotional dynamic explains why antisemitism endures despite contradictions or counter-evidence: it is not held because it is true, but because it is comforting (Sartre [1948] 1976:13–18). For Sartre, these emotional and cognitive dynamics ultimately point to a deeper existential claim: the anti-Semite is responsible for his hatred because he has chosen it. Antisemitism is not the product of ignorance, misinformation, or upbringing, it is rather an attitude that the anti-Semite willingly adopts in order to avoid the restrictions of freedom and accountability. Sartre notes that by selecting antisemitism, the anti-Semite chooses to embrace a ready-made identity that frees him from the demands of self-reflection and responsibility (Sartre [1948] 1976:9–12). This posture allows the anti-Semite to hide within a collective myth instead of confronting the anxiety of authentic existence. In this sense, even self-deception involved is itself a choice for which consciousness remains accountable (Sartre [1943] 1956:70–72). Bottom line, Sartre’s thesis reveals that the anti-Semite’s perspective is not an error in logic, but a deliberate choice to reject good-faith reasoning. By manipulating language, the anti-Semite seeks to destabilize opponents who remain committed to truth and consistency, thereby creating a structural asymmetry in the discourse.

Post 7 October 2023: Applying Sartre

Sartre’s philosophical framework, even though developed decades earlier, remains strikingly relevant when applied to the patterns of antisemitism observed since October 7, 2023. The rapidity of antisemitic mobilization post-7 October 2023 can be interpreted, in Sartre’s terms, as not driven by new knowledge or real-time political analysis, but by a pre-existing worldview waiting for activation, a deep need to project blame, and a desire to evade freedom and complexity. As Sartre would predict, post-7 October 2023 demonstrations were marked not by new information but by the activation of a pre-existing interpretive framework. This fits his claim that antisemitism is a “passion” that precedes facts: events merely license the outward expression of an already chosen worldview (Sartre [1948] 1976:12). For instance, London demonstrations saw rhetorical convergence between far-left, far-right, and Islamist groups, consistent with Sartre’s account that antisemitism functions as an identity-simplifying narrative rather than a policy disagreement (CST 2024a; Stögner 2025:18). In New York, rallies outside major universities featured speakers blaming all Jews for the conflict and displaying banners

calling for the destruction of Israel (ADL 2024). The protests and rhetorical convergence across ideologically distant groups (far-right, far-left, and Islamist milieus) suggest that antisemitism functions as an organizing myth, not a reasoned critique of Israeli policies. Social media acted as a catalyst for this rapid diffusion of antisemitic content. However, not because the users were persuaded, but because they had already chosen the passion as Sartre describes it. In Sartre's view, the attacks did not generate hatred but legitimized its expression.

Antisemitism often operates by projecting abstract threats onto Jewish identity and simplifying complex realities into ideological certainties. This closely aligns with Sartre's notion of antisemitism as a passionate, pre-rational worldview (Stögner 2025:2, 18). Similarly, Greene's empirical findings that higher education correlates with greater discriminatory double standards give real-world grounding to Sartre's thesis that antisemitism is not correlated with facts but shields itself from them (Greene, Cheng, and Kingsbury 2021:6-7, 10-12).

Sartre links antisemitism to the dehumanization of Jews, projecting them as fixed symbols for simplifying the world for the anti-Semite. For instance, holocaust-related antisemitism and comparisons between Israel and the Nazis directly dehumanize Jews by linking them to one of the most evil regimes in history, distorting their suffering, and accusing them of mirroring genocide (CST 2024a:34). Further examples include labeling young Jewish students as child murderers, which is a form of demonization rooted in blood libel (CST 2024b:24; Soyer 2025:Ch. 2), depicting Jews as Satanic is a classic dehumanizing trope meaning to strip them of humanity and morality (ADL 2024:5), as well as calling for "eradicating Zionism and all its supporters," which means the elimination of Jews. Further, Jews being visibly identifiable, by religious symbols, dress, or expressions of support for Israel, become targets not based on individual actions, but based on projected identity. 18 percent of Jews in the US experienced assault or threats because of their Jewish identity, which is why many remove their visible Jewish symbols out of fear (ADL and Jewish Federations of North America 2025:2-4). This fear of showing identity in public reflects the denial of existential freedom, a core Sartrean concern. In his terms, antisemitism pushes Jews into bad faith: denying or hiding aspects of themselves to survive. The public gaze functions as surveillance and moral policing, reducing political and existential freedom for Jewish individuals.

Furthermore, Sartre critiques the liberal belief in abstract individuals, ignoring concrete vulnerabilities. For him, authentic justice must be situated, and being neutral when Jews are attacked as Jews erases the very identity that is being attacked (Sartre [1948] 1976:39-41). This philosophical insight finds striking confirmation in recent empirical evidence. For instance, university administrators have failed to enforce their own anti-racism policies when Jewish students are harassed, treating them as abstract students rather than recognizing their particular vulnerability (CST 2024b:10). Similarly, Jewish complaints about abuse are often dismissed or downplayed in ways other minorities do not experience (CST 2024b:15), and Jewish employees are told they must tolerate hostility due to Israel's action, as if their Jewish identity were inseparable from foreign government's policies (CST 2025:13). These cases illustrate Sartre's point: when institutions apply abstract standards to concrete injustices, they fail to protect those whose identities are marked and marginalized. Neutrality, in such contexts, is not justice – it is abandonment. So, antisemitism, for him, is the rejection of universality disguised as fairness. Moreover, these examples show how passion precedes facts and then cherry-picks or re-reads evidence to fit it. Sartre diagnoses a rule application bias as the anti-Semite changes the rule when the subject is Jewish. A practical antidote is precisely to ask whether the person would judge the same behavior the same way if the actor were not Jewish, where Sartre says the anti-Semite's answer is systematically “no” (Sartre [1948] 1976:6-8, 12, 40). Further, the anti-Semite adopts moral discourse or language while applying it selectively. For instance, Israel-related topics are treated more controversially than other national conflicts, which treats one ethnic group's homeland more morally suspect than others, reinforcing the idea that only Jews must pass a higher ethical test to be accepted (CST 2024b:32). Another example is the use of anti-oppression rhetoric, which is invoked to label Jewish speakers “oppressors” or “settler colonists,” thus excluding them from the very conversations framed as inclusive and just (ADL 2024:4). In such cases, universal moral ideas are applied selectively, transforming ethical discourse into a tool of vilification. As Sartre warns, such false moralism disguises hatred in the language of virtue, allowing the anti-Semite to feel noble while enacting exclusion.

Antisemitism is an existential commitment, meaning it is not corrected by education alone because it organizes how the anti-Semite sees people, history, and society. Since the passion/ worldview precedes facts, information campaigns alone will not convert a committed anti-Semite, as the person would have to renounce the project. It is about the

way of being, to reduce the social payoffs of the project, protect those targeted, and appeal to freedom and authenticity among those still wavering. Sartre warns against treating antisemitism as a single opinion that could be refuted with a single counter-fact, as an interruption of the whole circuit (the passion, social setting, and incentives) is needed (Sartre [1948] 1976). Contemporary examples, such as when professors remained silent or even contributed while Jewish students were targeted (CST 2024b:10, 24) or the exclusion of Jewish students from programs meant to ensure inclusion (CST 2024b:32), show that more education does not necessarily reduce antisemitism.

Arendt's critique

While Sartre offers an existential account of antisemitism as a chosen passion, his framework has notable limitations. To grasp dimensions of antisemitism that his analysis under-specifies, Hannah Arendt (1906 – 1975) developed an explicitly contrasting approach. Arendt, a German and American historian and philosopher, views antisemitism not just as an irrational hatred or a psychological disorder, but as a political ideology that has developed over time, emerging particularly in nineteenth-century Europe and becoming an integral part of nationalist and totalitarian movements (Arendt 1973:vii-viii, xii, xvi). From this historically grounded perspective, Arendt links the emergence of antisemitic ideologies to the decline of the nation-state and the rise of imperialism, in which Jews became scapegoats within politically unstable and economically fragmented systems (Arendt 1973:xiv, xvi-xvii, 3-5). Although Arendt acknowledges that Jews were scapegoated, she avoids overly simplistic victim narratives. Instead, she focuses on Jewish assimilation, economic functions, and the changing relationship between Jews and state power (Arendt 1973:xii-xiv, 14-21). Moreover, Arendt rejects the idea of “eternal antisemitism,” which is the belief that Jew-hatred is a timeless, universal, and inevitable feature of human history, and that antisemitism is a “natural reaction to the presence of Jews, simply awaiting opportunities to erupt. To her, “eternal antisemitism” replaces political inquiry with fatalism, excuses antisemitic violence as inevitable, undermines both Jewish and non-Jewish agency, and prevents a historical understanding of antisemitism as a modern political ideology (Arendt 1973:7-8).

Arendt strongly disagrees with Sartre's reduction of Jewish identity to a product of antisemitic projection, arguing that this effaces Jewish history, culture, and political agency. In her view, Sartre's approach effectively denies Jews their right to self-definition by allowing the oppressor's perspective to determine who Jews are. This is an implication,

she considers both indefensible both philosophically and morally. Further, Arendt criticizes Sartre's focus on individual psychology as insufficient for understanding the structural role of antisemitism in society. She believes that Sartre overlooks how antisemitism is exploited politically, for instance, by totalitarian movements. Moreover, Arendt warns against depoliticizing antisemitism by portraying it as an individual's "passion." Her argument implies that such a narrative strips antisemitism of its real-world impact and disguises how it was used as a weapon by fascist regimes to justify genocide. Lastly, Arendt believes that Sartre unintentionally repeats the very logic he is trying to dismantle. By insisting that Jews exist only through the eyes of anti-Semites, Sartre adopts the structure of antisemitic essentialism and merely replaces race with gaze. For Arendt, this philosophical reversal does not liberate, but negates (Arendt 1973:6-8).

The increase in antisemitic incidents and the convergence of various ideological groups cannot be attributed solely to individual feelings or passions. Sartre's understanding of 'passion' is insufficient for explaining the mass political mobilizations where antisemitism is purposefully exploited. These surges in antisemitism are not merely natural reactions to Israeli actions or Jewish presence; rather, they reflect a dangerous alignment with the concept of 'eternal antisemitism.' Jewish individuals are pressured to conceal their identities or face accusations of complicity due to their heritage. This perspective risks endorsing an oppressive view that reduces Jewishness to a response to external attacks.

However, integrating Arendt's and Sartre's perspectives provides a more comprehensive understanding. Arendt's focus on antisemitism as a historical and political ideology complements Sartre's existential exploration of antisemitism as a passion. While Sartre emphasizes the emotional and rhetorical aspects that drive antisemitism, Arendt highlights its exploitation within political structures. Understanding antisemitism today requires recognizing it as both an individual existential choice and a structural ideology exploited for political purposes. To effectively address antisemitism, it is crucial to dismantle the frameworks that allow it to persist. This includes addressing the underlying political agendas that employ antisemitism to justify violence and exclusion. Both Sartre and Arendt underscore the need for collective responsibility in combating antisemitism, not only through education but also by challenging the structural conditions that perpetuate it.

Conclusion

The rise of antisemitism after October 7, 2023, underscores the need for an analytical and philosophical framework that accounts for both individual psychology and structural forces. Sartre's existential account shows how antisemitism can function as a self-chosen passion, one that simplifies complexity, displaces responsibility, and provides the anti-Semite with an emotionally coherent worldview. His analysis helps explain the rhetorical and affective mechanisms through which antisemitism can reappear today under the language of neutrality, justice, or critique. At the same time, Arendt's work reminds us that antisemitism cannot be reduced to individual attitudes alone. For her, it is a historically produced political ideology rooted in institutional failures, shifting power structures, and the crises of the modern nation-state. Both philosophers, Sartre and Arendt, argue that antisemitism must be confronted as an existential project that distorts identity and as a political weapon wielded to justify exclusion and violence. Effective combatment requires more than education and moral appeals; it demands structural accountability, protection of vulnerable communities, and a refusal to universalize neutrality in the face of targeted hate.

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